

LiveSkeleton: High-Quality Real-Time Human Tracking and Pose Estimation

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Abstract—We introduce *LiveSkeleton*, a high-performance human pose estimation algorithm designed for real-time multimedia applications. Our approach integrates robust person detection using Scaled-YoloV4, efficient optical-flow based tracking and the high-quality RTMPose algorithm for skeleton extraction. Operating at 25 frames per second for up to five individuals simultaneously, the system demonstrates robust performance across content from diverse scenarios, including VR/XR environments, surveillance contexts, and healthcare settings. Experimental results confirm that the algorithm performs well in challenging conditions, such as crowded scenes with substantial occlusion, thereby offering significant potential for enhancing human-computer interaction and automated behavior analysis.

Index Terms—human detection, human tracking, pose estimation, real-time processing, VR

I. INTRODUCTION

Real-time human pose (skeleton) estimation holds significant value across a broad spectrum of applications because it facilitates the instant analysis and understanding of human movements and actions as they occur. In sports and fitness, this technology provides immediate feedback on posture and technique, which is crucial for helping athletes refine their performance and reduce the risk of injuries. In healthcare, it can assist in monitoring the rehabilitation progress of a patient or detecting falls in the elderly. In gaming and virtual reality, it enhances user interaction by enabling more natural and responsive control. Moreover, in security and surveillance, it contributes to the detection of suspicious behavior and critical situations. The capability to process this data in real-time unlocks new opportunities for creating interactive systems, delivering personalized experiences, and developing responsive environments that adapt to user’s needs.

So far, only a few works (e.g. [5]) in the literature address the task of simultaneous detection, tracking and pose estimation of humans in video – and none of them claims to be real-time capable. Motivated by this, we propose the *LiveSkeleton* algorithm, which is able to perform human detection, tracking and pose (skeleton) estimation in real-time for different modalities like videos captured with a RGB camera, thermal camera or rendered VR/XR content. We describe the proposed algorithm and its main components in section II, in section III a qualitative evaluation of the algorithm is presented and section IV concludes the paper.

II. ALGORITHM

The proposed algorithm is composed of two main components. The first component (see subsection II-A) deals with robust detection and tracking of humans in video, whereas the second component (see subsection II-B) is responsible for the subsequent pose (skeleton) estimation for all detected humans.

A crucial factor for achieving real-time performance is to let both components operate *in parallel*, instead of a invoking them serially. This means that the pose estimation for the *last* frame and the human detection and tracking for the *current* frame is done *simultaneously*.

As common deep learning frameworks like *PyTorch* do not allow the simultaneous inference of two different models, we resort to the *multiprocessing* package¹ available in Python. The multiprocessing package enables the creation of multiple processes, each running independently on separate cores, to efficiently parallelize tasks and improve performance on multi-core systems.

A. Human detection and tracking

For the real-time detection and tracking of humans in video, we employ a similar workflow as proposed in [1]. We utilize the powerful object detector *Scaled-YoloV4* [4] and combine it with the RAFT optical flow algorithm [3] for tracking.

In the following, the object detection and tracking algorithm is outlined briefly. Let I_{t-1} and I_t represent two consecutive frames at timepoints $t-1$ and t , and S_{t-1} be the list of scene objects that have been tracked up to timepoint $t-1$. The workflow for processing each frame can be divided into five phases:

- *Preprocessing*: General preparation steps, such as down-scaling, are performed on the input image I_t (the current video frame).
- *Feature calculation*: The optical flow between the (down-scaled) frames I_{t-1} and I_t is computed, resulting in a dense motion field M_{t-1} . Additionally, the object detector is invoked for I_t , generating a list of detected objects D_t .
- *Tracking*: The motion of all scene objects S_{t-1} is predicted (using the motion field) to infer their new positions S_t for timepoint t .

¹<https://docs.python.org/3/library/multiprocessing.html>

- *Matching*: The optimal matching between the tracked scene objects S_t and detected objects D_t is calculated via the Hungarian algorithm.
- *Update*: Any scene objects in S_t that cannot be matched are flagged as lost and excluded from processing. Any unmatched detected objects in D_t are treated as newly appearing and added to the scene objects list S_t .

For optimal performance we run the optical flow algorithm in parallel to the object detection and invoke the object detector only for every second frame.

B. Human pose estimation

For the human pose estimation, we employ the recently proposed *RTMPose* algorithm [2]. It relies on the detected human bounding boxes and returns for each bounding box the estimated human pose (skeleton) in the COCO format (17 keypoints for the skeleton).

RTMPose adopts *CSPNetXt* as the network backbone, which shows a good balance of speed and accuracy and is furthermore deployment-friendly. The keypoint prediction is formulated as a coordinate classification problem (instead of the usual heatmap-based approach), which allows for a very compact architecture that requires neither high-resolution intermediate representations nor costly upscaling layers.

We use the *RTMPose* implementation from the *MMPose*² library. From the available pretrained model variants there, we choose the *RTMPose-m* variant.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND TESTS

For the runtime measurements we employ a Windows 10 PC with a Intel Core i7-12700 CPU and NVIDIA Geforce RTX 3090 GPU. We measure the average runtime per frame on sequences with different resolutions, from standard definition (800 × 600) to Full HD (1920 × 1080). The average runtime of the human detection and tracking component is 35 – 40 milliseconds per frame. The pose estimation takes roughly 7 – 9 milliseconds for each detected human, so we achieve real-time performance (40 milliseconds per frame, 25 frames per second) for up to five humans visible in the scene. As both components run in parallel (see section II), this means that the *LiveSkeleton* algorithm runs in real-time (25 fps) for up to five humans in the scene.

We perform also an initial qualitative evaluation of the poses (skeletons) estimated by the *LiveSkeleton* algorithm. In order to get a indication of the quality and robustness of the algorithm for different applications, we use test videos of different modalities: Rendered VR scenes created with Unity, standard videos captured with a RGB video and videos captured with a thermal camera. As can be seen in Figure 1, we observe that the result is of high quality for all modalities. Furthermore, the algorithm works well also for crowds with significant occlusions. A demo video is available online³.

²<https://github.com/open-mmlab/mmpose>

³https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RLMt8kWP_o9NdTC4uTIInmEe1VIM693vO/view

Fig. 1. Visualization of human pose estimation with *LiveSkeleton* algorithm for rendered/VR content (top left), thermal camera video (top right) and standard RGB camera video (bottom).

IV. CONCLUSION

We propose *LiveSkeleton*, a high-performance human pose estimation algorithm tailored for real-time multimedia applications. Via a combination of high-quality and runtime-efficient methods for human detection, tracking and pose estimation we achieve real-time performance (25 fps) for up to five humans in the scene. It performs reliably across various scenarios and is robust even in challenging conditions.

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